

Structural properties of inkjet-printed and ultrasound-spray-coated PEM fuel cell catalyst layers and their impact on fuel cell performance

M. Hala^a, M. Prokop^a, P. Capek^b, M. Vesely^b, T. Jedlicka^a, T. Zubkova^c, K. Heinrich^c, A. Willert^c, R. Zichner^c, K. Bouzek^{a,*}

^a Department of Inorganic Technology, University of Chemistry and Technology Prague, Technická 5, Prague 6, 166 28, Czech Republic

^b Department of Organic Technology, University of Chemistry and Technology Prague, Technická 5, Prague 6, 166 28, Czech Republic

^c Fraunhofer Institute for Electronic Nano Systems, Technologie-Campus 3, 09126, Chemnitz, Germany

ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:

PEM
Fuel cell
Inkjet printing
Catalyst layer
Electrical conductivity
Permeability
Porosity
Tomography

ABSTRACT

Catalyst layers (CLs) are critical to the performance and durability of proton exchange membrane fuel cells (PEMFCs). As shown previously, inkjet printing (IJP) represents an attractive CL production technology ensuring efficient catalyst utilization. This study provides a comparative structural analysis of CLs fabricated via IJP and ultrasonic spray coating (USC), aiming to explain the performance differences observed in operating fuel cells utilizing these two types of CL. This allows further optimisation of the CL deposition by IJP. A combination of advanced experimental and modeling techniques was employed to accomplish this task, including in-plane electron conductivity measurements, optical profilometry, FIB-SEM tomography, and 3D structure-based transport simulations. IJP CLs were consistently thinner (4–10 μm vs. 6–18 μm), smoother ($R_a \sim 0.38\text{--}0.44 \mu\text{m}$ vs. $\sim 0.55\text{--}0.63 \mu\text{m}$), and exhibited significantly fewer surface cracks (0.18–0.61 % vs. 1.34–4.05 %) compared to USC layers. Despite similar porosities at the microscale (40.0 % for IJP vs. 38.3 % for USC), IJP layers showed higher electrical conductivity ($448 \pm 135 \text{ S m}^{-1}$ vs. $387 \pm 96 \text{ S m}^{-1}$) and more homogeneous Pt distribution. FIB-SEM reconstructions confirmed isotropic and statistically homogeneous structures of CLs produced by both methods, with negligible isolated porosity and comparable transport properties. However, macroscale features such as crack formation, layer thickness, and surface roughness strongly impacted overall performance and Pt utilization. These results highlight the critical role of deposition method in determining catalyst layer architecture and reveal inkjet printing as a highly promising approach for producing low-loading, high-performance CLs with potential for scalable, additive manufacturing.

List of symbols

Symbol	Units	Description
a	m	Distance a between two adjacent lattice nodes
A	m^2	Electrode surface area
$ECSA$	$\text{m}^2 \text{g}^{-1}$	Electrochemical surface area
g_{eff}	1	Effective electrical conductivity
h	μm	CL thickness
I	A	Electrical current
$f^{(s)}(\mathbf{x})$	1	Indicator function for the solid phase

(continued on next column)

(continued)

$f^{(v)}(\mathbf{x})$	1	Indicator function for the void phase
$l_1, l_2, \text{ and } l_3$	1	Integers
$m_{\text{A,Pt}}$	$\frac{\text{mg}}{\text{cm}^2}$	Pt loading
N	1	Sampling area (number of pixels)
$P^{(v)}(\delta)$	μm^{-1}	Pore-size probability density function
$q_{\text{H,ML}}$	C m^{-2}	Charge of adsorbed hydrogen monolayer
R_a	μm	Arithmetic mean roughness
R_q	μm	Root mean ² roughness

(continued on next page)

Abbreviations: PEMFC, Proton exchange membrane fuel cell; CCM, Catalyst coated membrane; FIB-SEM, Focused ion beam scanning electron microscopy; FIB-TEM, Focused ion beam transmission electron microscopy; IJP, Inkjet printing; IQR, Interquartile range; USC, Ultrasonic spray coating; CNC, Computer numerical control; FTO, Fluorine-doped tin oxide; GDL, Gas diffusion layer; MPL, Microporous layer; MEA, Membrane electrode assembly; CL, catalyst layer; R2R, roll-to-roll; X-ray CT, X-ray computer tomography; EDS, energy-dispersive spectroscopy; CF, crack fraction; NaN, not a number; R_a , Arithmetic Mean Square Roughness; R_q , Root Mean Square Roughness.

* Corresponding author.

E-mail address: bouzekk@vscht.cz (K. Bouzek).

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cej.2025.171283>

Received 5 September 2025; Received in revised form 3 November 2025; Accepted 25 November 2025

Available online 26 November 2025

1385-8947/© 2025 The Authors. Published by Elsevier B.V. This is an open access article under the CC BY license (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).

(continued)

s	$\text{m}^2 \text{m}^{-3}$	Specific surface
$S^{(v)}(\mathbf{x})$	1	One point probability function for the void phase
S_{bulk}	S m^{-1}	Average bulk electrical conductivity
S_{CL}	S m^{-1}	Catalyst layer electrical conductivity
U_{lb}	V	Lower boundary voltage
U_{ub}	V	Upper boundary voltage
V	–	Convex region of space filled by the medium
v	V s^{-1}	Scan rate
w_i	1	Mass fraction of component/phase i
\mathbf{x}	μm	Position vector $\mathbf{x} = (x_1, x_2, x_3) = (a_1, a_2, a_3)$
z_i	μm	Local height of CL
\bar{z}	μm	Mean height of CL (averaged over all pixels in the map)
β	m^2	Transport parameter
δ	m	Distance between the nearest point on the pore-solid interface
ϕ_v	1	Total porosity
ϕ_{vi}	1	Isolated porosity
κ	m	Transport parameter
σ_β	m^2	Joint confidence limit for β
σ_κ	m	Joint confidence limit for κ
Ψ_{ii}	1	Calculated geometric factor

1. Introduction

Proton exchange membrane fuel cells (PEMFCs) represent a key technology for decarbonisation across transportation and stationary power sectors due to their high energy conversion efficiency and compact design [1–4]. However, large-scale adoption is limited by high catalyst costs and performance variability, both of which are closely linked to the structure and fabrication method of the catalyst layer (CL). As the functional site for electrochemical reactions, the CL architecture influences catalyst utilization, gas transport, ionic and electron conductivity, and durability [5–8].

To maximize performance, CLs are often deposited directly onto the membrane, forming a catalyst coated membrane (CCM). This approach enhances the connection between ion conductive phases and significantly improves PEMFC performance [9]. In addition to composition, the deposition technique chosen for production of CCMs plays a crucial role in determining the structural and functional properties of CLs. Advanced methods allowing precise control over the structure and composition of CCMs are essential, particularly in considering economic factors such as process scalability and waste reduction. Among the large-scale manufacturing methods, roll-to-roll (R2R) techniques, such as slot-die coating, are commonly reported for high-throughput production of membrane electrode assemblies (MEAs) with identical geometry [10,11].

Additive manufacturing technologies, such as inkjet printing (IJP) offer an attractive alternative. IJP deposits the catalyst ink onto the membrane surface in a highly controlled manner using piezoelectric actuators. This technique is particularly advantageous for producing low platinum loaded layers with high precision and minimal material waste [12–23]. Additionally, IJP is characterized by high flexibility and variability, allowing for rapid on-demand deposition of customized structures and graded catalyst layer geometries enhancing utilization of Pt and/or efficiency of the electrochemical processes [24–26]. This makes IJP highly attractive and suitable for a wide range of applications at small to medium production rates.

Ultrasonic spray coating (USC) is a widely used scalable technique for CCM fabrication [46–48]. It can use catalyst inks of identical, or similar, composition as IJP, while it relies on a different deposition technique based on atomization of the ink with the following gravitational deposition of the formed droplets to substrate. In contrast to the other layer deposition methods, both the USC and IJP are scalable from laboratory application to industrial production. This makes USC both an industrially relevant benchmark and a counterpoint in the deposition mechanism to IJP allowing us to separate effects of the deposition method and the composition of the ink.

Our previous study [27] demonstrated that CLs produced by

industrial-scale IJP outperformed those deposited by USC, particularly at low platinum loadings. This superior performance was linked to differences in internal structure and transport properties resulting from the chosen deposition technique. To achieve a deeper and more accurate understanding of CL morphology, advanced imaging tools such as focused ion beam scanning electron microscopy (FIB-SEM), transmission electron microscopy (FIB-TEM), and X-ray computed tomography (X-ray CT) are increasingly utilized [8,28–36]. Structural investigations of IJP catalyst layers have been reported by others, including Shukla et al. [22,37] and M. Sabharwal et al. [38], who provided valuable insights using methods such as SEM cross-section analysis, mercury porosimetry, and FIB-SEM reconstruction. However, most studies typically focused on selected structural features and analysis methods, without comparison to other fabrication methods and actual performance in an experimental fuel cell.

To achieve a deeper understanding of how deposition influences catalyst layer functionality, a comprehensive approach that builds directly on the performance data from our previous work [27] was adopted in this study. The aim was to compare side-by-side IJP and USC produced catalyst layer using identical inks and substrates. This approach allows to eliminate other parameters and to link observed differences in the performance exclusively to the deposition technique used. By combining high-resolution FIB-SEM tomography, optical profilometry, electron conductivity measurements, numerical simulation and experimental determination of transport parameters of CLs produced by IJP and USC, a critical set of information was collected. These techniques were used as a compromise between adequate resolution and sufficient size of the imaged/reconstructed region, which was necessary to draw relevant conclusions. It explains the performance differences observed in operating PEMFCs and assess the structural advantages of IJP for scalable, high-efficiency MEA production. This knowledge is crucial for further optimisation of the ink formulation and printing process parameters.

2. Experimental

For the comparison purposes, an ink with standard composition, suitable for both, the inkjet printing and ultrasonic spray coating, was developed and optimised. This was necessary in order to compare properties induced by the CL deposition method, while eliminating potential impact of the ink composition.

2.1. Ink preparation

The catalyst ink was prepared by mixing 4.7 g of ionomer dispersion Nafion™ D521, 5 wt%, (Chemours), 0.557 g Pt/C catalyst TEC10V30E (Tanaka Kikinzoku) in 27.8 g of water:alcohol mixture (30:70). The mixture was sonicated in an ultrasonic bath for 20 min and subsequently treated for 10 min (pulse 0.5 s) with ultrasonic probe to homogenize the ink and break up agglomerates.

2.2. Catalyst layer deposition

Two experimental methods of catalyst layer deposition were used, IJP and USC. In order to compare reliably properties of CLs deposited by both techniques, deposition parameters were kept constant, independently of the substrate type.

2.2.1. Inkjet-printing

For the inkjet printing Q-Class Sapphire QS-256/80 industrial printhead (Fujifilm Dimatix, USA) was used. The native drop volume of each nozzle is $80 \cdot 10^{-3} \mu\text{m}^3$. The native resolution of the printhead is 100 dpi, corresponding to the distance between the nozzles of 254 μm . The QS-printhead was driven by the PixDRO LP50 (SÜSS MicroTec SE, Germany). Further details and printing process optimization are described in our previous study [27].

2.2.2. Ultrasonic spray coating

Catalyst layers were deposited using an in-house made system, consisting of an ultrasonication nozzle with integrated focusing N₂ gas delivery (50 cm³ min⁻¹) with a controller (Cheersonic), integrated into an x-y-z CNC platform (CZ Robotics). Details of the deposition are described in our previous study [27].

2.3. Catalyst layer electron conductivity

Electron conductivity of prepared layers was determined using procedure described in previous work [30]. Catalyst layers were deposited using procedures described in Sections 2.2.1 and 2.2.2 on a fluorine-doped tin oxide (FTO) glass TCO22-7/LI (Solaronics) with conductivity of 286,500 S m⁻¹ and thickness of 500 nm. A series of CL samples was prepared with Pt loading varying between 0.1 and 0.3 mg cm⁻². The list of the samples tested is summarized in Table 1. Due to the nature of the layer surface, the thickness of the catalyst layers was determined using profilometry data analysed by four distinct methods:

- 1) Smooth 95 Percentile Method: This method calculates the layer thickness as the 95th percentile of the smoothed height profile. The uncertainty is determined from the standard deviation of the top 10 % of the height values.
- 2) Average Regions Max Method: The height profile is divided into five equal regions, and the average height of each region is calculated. The thickness is determined as the height of the highest region, and the uncertainty is derived from the standard deviation of the regional averages.
- 3) Average Regions Min Method: The height profile is divided into five equal regions, and the average height of each region is calculated. The thickness is determined as the height of the region with the lowest thickness, and the uncertainty is derived from the standard deviation of the regional averages.
- 4) Compact Layer Method: This method applies strong smoothing to the height profile to eliminate surface roughness. The compact layer is identified using the interquartile range (IQR) to exclude outliers, and the thickness is calculated as the mean height of the compact layer. The uncertainty is determined from the standard deviation of the heights within the compact layer.

Each method provides complementary insights into the layer thickness, accounting for different structural features and measurement uncertainties. The results were compared, and the 4) Compact Layer Method was selected as the most suitable one. The profilometry measurements were performed using a DektakXT profilometer (Bruker) in line mode across the entire catalyst layer, with normalization against

Table 1

Pt loading and thickness of catalyst layers on FTO glass based on the Compact Layer method used for the evaluation of electrical conductivity.

Sample ID	Pt loading / mg cm ⁻²	Thickness / μm
FTO_USC-1	0.097	6.89 ± 0.83
FTO_USC-2	0.104	7.74 ± 1.06
FTO_USC-3	0.167	9.79 ± 0.85
FTO_USC-4	0.164	9.29 ± 0.95
FTO_USC-5	0.217	12.67 ± 1.05
FTO_USC-6	0.217	13.28 ± 0.91
FTO_USC-7	0.294	16.17 ± 1.09
FTO_USC-8	0.311	17.52 ± 1.11
FTO_IJP-1	0.089	4.21 ± 0.62
FTO_IJP-2	0.091	4.38 ± 0.72
FTO_IJP-3	0.132	7.01 ± 0.48
FTO_IJP-4	0.150	5.20 ± 0.51
FTO_IJP-5	0.180	8.13 ± 0.46
FTO_IJP-6	0.175	9.00 ± 0.62
FTO_IJP-7	0.236	9.22 ± 0.64
FTO_IJP-8	0.239	8.99 ± 0.89

uncoated, flat sections of FTO glass. The results from all methods were compared to ensure robustness and consistency in the thickness evaluation.

Determination of in-plane electron conductivity was performed using the four-electrode setup described in [30] using chronopotentiometric DC current polarisation with potentiostat PARSTAT MC (Ametek) ranging from 1 to 10 mA. Resistance of layer was evaluated using 3D mathematical model of potential distribution in sample defined by Laplace equation.

The bulk conductivity of a fully compressed CL was measured using the method developed in [30]. A catalyst layer removed from the FTO glass and homogenized was used for this experiment. From the graph of the dependence of the layer's electrical conductivity on reciprocal compression level, the value of conductivity at maximum compression level was extrapolated.

2.4. Catalyst layer permeability

The method used to obtain effective transport properties of the catalyst layer involved quasi-stationary permeation experiments using pure gases at ambient temperature. Due to the mechanical instability of the CL, it was deposited on a SIGRACET 38BC gas diffusion layer (GDL), allowing for the estimation of transport parameters by first measuring the GDL alone and then the GDL with the CL. The permeation cell consisted of two chambers separated by impermeable discs with a cylindrical opening, where the porous sample is fastened. The mathematical model assumed quasi-stationary gas transport in multilayer porous media and allowed the estimation of effective transport parameters appearing in the Darcy equation modified for gas transport. Further details on this method can be found in previous work [30].

2.5. Optical surface characterization

Optical observation and surface roughness of prepared samples on Sigracet 38BC GDL were carried out by optical profilometry Sensofar S Neox (Sensofar) working in confocal mode. The confocal Z-scanning were performed using 20× objective (TU Plan Fluor EPI, Nikon) with vertical resolution of 5 nm and pixel size of 0.69 μm. To cover statistically significant area of the sample surface comparable to the sample area exposed to the gas permeation in the permeation cell, 4 × 3 field-of-views for each sample was acquired. After installation, the total inspected area of the sample was 3.15 mm × 2.37 mm. The final sample map recorded contained two types of pixels: I) pixels with information about the height in case that the light from microscope illumination went through the focus, and II) pixels with “Not-a-number” value in case of the light did not find a focus within the total scanning depth of 100 μm. In the case of these materials, the “Not-a-number” values typically indicate cracks in the sample surface.

Due to a natural tilt of the sample on the large inspected area, the resulting map was corrected for sample tilt by identifying the background. The background correction was based on morphological opening, which was applied only on homogeneous part of the map; i.e., all the pixels containing height values. As a structuring element, the disc with a diameter of 20 pixels was used. The background subtracted map was consequently processed to calculate characteristics to quantify surface roughness [39], the Arithmetic Mean Roughness (R_a , Eq. (1)) and the Root Mean Square Roughness (R_q , Eq. (2))

$$R_a = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N |z_i - \bar{z}| \quad (1)$$

$$R_q = \sqrt{\frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N (z_i - \bar{z})^2} \quad (2)$$

where N is the number of pixels in the sampling area, z_i is the local height (layer thickness) at pixel i and \bar{z} is the mean height over all pixels

in the map.

To quantify the extent of cracks, we introduced Crack fraction (CF), which is the ratio of “Not-a-number” pixels divided by total amount of pixels in the map.

2.6. 3D imaging of catalyst layers

For the 3D imaging, a dual beam Lyra 3 GMU instrument (Tescan-Orsay) equipped with a high-power electron beam and a gallium ion column was used. The details of the data acquisition procedure are described in a recent paper [29] with one exception, which is the voxel size. By fine-tuning the whole procedure, the voxel size was reduced to 5 nm, which allowed following microstructural details at a higher resolution. Raw 2D images had to be re-aligned, cropped and packaged into one volumetric (3D) image for each material. After correcting for uneven illumination in the 3D images, these images were further processed by filtering in the spatial domain. A proven combination of an adaptive median filter and an anisotropic 3D diffusion filter was used to adjust the images prior to segmentation. Subsequent segmentation was performed using a graph-based algorithm called power watershed. The details of the entire procedure are again described in paper [29].

2.7. Mathematical description of microstructure

The structure of the digitised catalyst layer consisting of the void and solid phases can be defined in terms of the indicator function for the void phase (Eq. (3)) [40].

$$I^{(v)}(\mathbf{x}) = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if } \mathbf{x} \text{ belongs to the void phase} \\ 0, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

where \mathbf{x} is the position vector, $\mathbf{x} \in \mathbb{V}$, and \mathbb{V} is the convex region of space filled by the medium. Discrete values of $\mathbf{x} = (x_1, x_2, x_3)$ are determined by a simple cubic lattice of size $a l_1 \times a l_2 \times a l_3$ in the 3D medium. The distance a between two adjacent lattice nodes corresponds to the cubic voxel size, and l_1, l_2 , and l_3 are integers. Note that there is the simple functional relationship between the indicator functions for the void and solid phases: $I^{(v)}(\mathbf{x}) + I^{(s)}(\mathbf{x}) = 1$. The mathematical model of the microstructure represented by the indicator function is subsequently referred to as the replica. It is also worth noting that the third coordinate (x_3) is related to the thickness of the catalyst layers.

In order to show basic statistical characteristics of region \mathbb{V} in a condensed form, the one-point probability function, $S_1^{(v)}(\mathbf{x})$, was computed for the void phase in three principal directions. The function $S_1^{(v)}(\mathbf{x})$ gives the probability of finding the void phase at the position \mathbf{x} and is interpreted as a position-dependent volume fraction of the void phase [40]. If the values of this function are independent of position, the microstructure is said to be statistically homogeneous. Consequently, an ergodic hypothesis holds, i.e., one sufficiently voluminous region \mathbb{V} provides complete probabilistic information. It is also meaningful to define volume averages for \mathbb{V} . Since the region \mathbb{V} had a relatively small volume (due to the limits of FIB-SEM), the function $S_1^{(v)}(\mathbf{x})$ allowed us to test whether the ergodic hypothesis was valid and whether a volume of the region \mathbb{V} was large enough to evaluate volume averages (effective transport properties here). Averaging $S_1^{(v)}(\mathbf{x})$ over the entire region \mathbb{V} gives the mean void fraction (Eq. (4)).

$$\phi_v = \int_{\mathbb{V}} S_1^{(v)}(\mathbf{x}) d\mathbf{x} \quad (4)$$

To characterize pore sizes of \mathbb{V} , a microstructural descriptor called the pore-size probability density function $P^{(v)}(\delta)$ was chosen. The product $P^{(v)}(\delta) d\delta$ represents the probability that a randomly chosen point in the pore space lies at a distance between δ and $\delta + d\delta$ from the nearest point on the pore-solid interface [40]. Note that the definition assumes the statistically homogeneous microstructure in \mathbb{V} . Since only

one realization of \mathbb{V} for each catalyst layer was available, the ergodic hypothesis in the calculation of the $P^{(v)}(\delta)$ function had to be used. The function $P^{(v)}$ has the two extreme values (Eqs. (5) and (6))

$$P^{(v)}(0) = s/\phi_v \quad (5)$$

$$P^{(v)}(\infty) = 0 \quad (6)$$

where s stands for the specific surface defined to be the interface area per unit volume of \mathbb{V} . The complementary cumulative probability function $F^{(v)}(\delta)$ complemented the function $P^{(v)}(\delta)$ (Eq. (7)).

$$F^{(v)}(\delta) = \int_{\delta}^{\infty} P^{(v)}(r) dr \quad (7)$$

Put another way, $F^{(v)}(\delta)$ is the fraction of pore space that has a pore radius larger than δ . By analogy, the functions $P^{(s)}(\delta)$ and $F^{(s)}(\delta)$ for the solid phase were also calculated. A mean radius of spherical regions of phase i was also used (Eq. (8)).

$$\langle \delta_i \rangle = \int_0^{\infty} \delta P^{(i)}(\delta) d\delta = \int_0^{\infty} F^{(i)}(\delta) d\delta \quad (8)$$

Connectivity of the void phase was characterized using the two-point cluster function $C_2^{(v)}(\mathbf{x}_1, \mathbf{x}_2)$ [40]. For a statistically homogeneous medium, the function is defined as the probability that both ends of a line segment of length $u = \|\mathbf{x}_2 - \mathbf{x}_1\|$ tossed at random into the medium are located in the same cluster of the void phase. Note that the 26-neighbour connectivity rule was used for clustering of the void-phase voxels.

In order to verify the pore structure information obtained by the 3D imaging and subsequent mathematical treatment, pore size estimation with mercury porosimetry was determined using AutoPore IV (Micromeritics) porosimeter and BET surface area was obtained using ASAP 2050 (Micromeritics) extended pressure adsorption analyzer.

3. Results and discussion

In the following text, individual characteristics of the CLs produced by the IJP and by the USC are determined and compared. The aim is to link these properties to the CL performance in the fuel cells reported previously [27]. This allows gaining deeper understanding of the deposition method impact on the catalyst layer functionality and, consequently, fuel cell performance. As can be found in the Fig. S1 in Supplementary information, the IJP layers exhibit high activity and efficient catalyst utilization at low cathode loadings ($0.1 \text{ mg}_{\text{Pt}} \text{ cm}^{-2}$). As catalyst loading increases, however, the load curves show transition toward transport-limited behaviour. In contrast, USC layers show kinetically hindered performance at low loading. With increasing loading both mass and charge transport are improved resulting in improved fuel cell performance. This leads to the similar peak power performance of IJP layers with $0.1 \text{ mg}_{\text{Pt}} \text{ cm}^{-2}$ catalyst loading and USC layers with $0.3 \text{ mg}_{\text{Pt}} \text{ cm}^{-2}$.

3.1. SEM microscopy

The first insights into the morphological characteristics of the catalyst layers were obtained using scanning electron microscopy (SEM). This method enabled the visual assessment of surface texture, crack patterns, and deposition-related artefacts, forming the basis for subsequent quantitative and structural analyses. It is important to keep on our mind, that these CL defects have potential influence on the fuel cell performance, e.g. due to the impact on the CL longitudinal conductivity, or water management. Whereas Fig. 1 summarises typical morphologies of CLs produced by USC and by IJP, Fig. 2 provides results of the surface EDS analysis. Samples USC 10L (i.e. 10 layers) and IJP 6L are displayed here because they were also used for the structure reconstruction, and sample USC 20L is displayed to show the contrast between samples with low and high Pt loading. Results obtained for the remaining samples are

Fig. 1. SEM images of USC 10L (A, B, C,) and IJP 6L (E, F, G) at $\times 50$ (A, E), $\times 250$ (B, F) and $\times 1000$ (C, G), detail of the spheres (I), and cross-sections of USC (D) and IJP (H) CCMs.

provided in Figs. S2 to S5 in the Supplementary information. Following conclusions may be derived from these observations. Firstly, the USC layers exhibit more visible cracks with sharper edges compared to the IJP layers. This can be attributed to differences in the thickness of a single deposited layer and the drying rates between the two methods. Individual layers deposited by USC contain more material and are drying more rapidly. This leads to an increased stress and more pronounced

crack formation. Secondly, in the IJP sample, repeating parallel lines are evident. This is clearly result of the printing process. Despite this, surface morphology indicates more compact and ordered CL structure in the case of CL produced by IJP. This coincides with the profilometry results (see Section 3.2, Table 2). Surprisingly, on the surface of the USC layers, spherical particles of 5 μm in radius may be observed. EDS analysis confirmed these structures to be of the same composition as the CL

Fig. 2. EDS analysis of Pt (A, E, I), F (B, F, J), C (C, G, K) of samples IJP 6L (A, B, C, D), USC 10L (E, F, G, H) and USC 20L (I, J, K, L) and corresponding SEM images (D, H, L).

Table 2

Crack fraction, R_a and R_q numbers for USC and IJP samples. SIGRACET 38BC is used as GDL.

Sample	Crack fraction / %	R_a / μm	R_q / μm
USC 10L	4.0478	0.550	0.640
USC 20L	4.1603	0.625	0.745
USC 30L	2.5032	0.570	0.635
USC 40L	1.3394	0.625	0.730
IJP 6L	0.6187	0.375	0.195
IJP 9L	0.5357	0.390	0.210
IJP 12L	0.3276	0.400	0.200
IJP 15L	0.1760	0.440	0.250
GDL	1.3542	0.398	0.235

surface. Accordingly, the spherical particles were identified as drops of the ink dried in-flight before impacting the surface of the CCM [41]. Some of these particles disperse when next layers are deposited onto them, as seen in cross-section images of catalyst layers (Fig. 1D)). Thirdly, as Fig. 2 shows, Pt was located in unconnected islands in the

case of USC 10L. These islands were not present anymore in the USC 20L sample, leading to a more homogeneous catalyst and ionomer distribution. This demonstrates the USC method is not suitable for deposition of CLs with low Pt loadings. In contrast to this, even IJP 6L shows homogeneous Pt distribution.

3.2. Optical profilometry

Whereas SEM provides qualitative images of surface features, optical profilometry allows to quantify surface roughness and crack distribution across representative areas. A combination of these two methods gives a comprehensive picture of surface morphology and layer integrity. This information is important for the following structural evaluation. An overview optical image was acquired (see Fig. 3A and B) to navigate over the sample and to identify the field-of-views for confocal scanning. Overview images of all samples can be found in Figs. S6 and S7. The *Not a Number (NaN)* pixels corresponding to the cracks are used to determine Crack Fraction of the sample surface. The Crack Fraction value is calculated based on binarization of the confocal image into the region of

Fig. 3. (A, B) Optical overview image of sample USC 20L (A) and IJP 12L (B). Cracks (black whiskers) are statistically significant feature of the sample surface for all investigated samples. (C, D) Confocal profilometry of sample USC 20L (C) and IJP 12L (D). Color bar denotes to the normalized, background subtracted, height of the sample surface. White areas in the images represent NaN values. (E, F) Binary image of the USC 20L (E) and IJP 12L (F) surface. Black pixels denote to regular homogeneous surface, white pixels denote to cracks in the surface.

the homogeneous material and regions with cracks (Fig. 3E) and F)).

In addition to crack fraction quantification, confocal profilometry image was also used to calculate Arithmetic Mean Roughness (R_a), and Root Mean Square Roughness (R_q). The R_a value shall be interpreted as average height of the peaks and valleys on the surface. R_q value is more sensitive to higher peaks and deeper valleys than R_a value. Lower R_q values correspond to more uniform/flat surface.

The resulting values are summarized in Table 2 for USC and IJP samples and substrate GDLs. Following conclusions may be derived from the analysis performed:

- GDLs used show homogeneous properties and do not have any effect on the properties of CLs deposited.

- USC prepared CLs show rougher surface with higher number of the well-pronounced cracks. These cracks are formed during the deposition process and their number decreases with the number of layers deposited.
- IJP produced CLs are generally smoother and more homogeneous. During printing, catalyst ink fills cracks occurring in the previous layer, including the GDL substrate. This leads to a significantly less disturbed CL.
- Smoothness of the CLs produced depends solely on the deposition method and does not change with the number of the layers deposited. These results are in contrast to crack formation behaviour of the CLs printed on membranes from our previous study [27]. There, the thicker CLs (more individual layers) exhibited higher crack fraction. These differences stem from the mechanism of the ink-substrate

interaction – the membrane swells and wrinkles in contact with the ink and the ink dries slower, while the GDL is not affected by the wetting of its surface by the ink and has a higher heat transfer coefficient leading to faster ink drying rate.

3.3. Porosity estimated from apparent and skeletal densities of CL

Following the characterization of surface morphology, the next step was to estimate the porosity of the layers based on the known composition and the thickness determined via profilometry. This approach provides a bulk-level assessment and serves as a first comparison of structural differences induced by the deposition method.

Firstly, thickness of the layer deposited on top of the FTO glass needs to be determined. The results obtained using the Compact Layer method are summarized in Fig. 4 (comparison of all the methods can be found in Fig. S8 in Supplementary information). As can be seen, CL layer thickness increased linearly with the Pt loading for both methods. USC layers, however, were consistently thicker than IJP layers with the same Pt loading. This suggests that USC formed CLs characterized by a less dense/more open structure.

The mass, composition and thickness of the CLs can be transformed into the total porosity ϵ_v using Eq. (9) [15,42].

$$\epsilon_v = 1 - \frac{m_{Pt}}{L} \left(\frac{1}{\rho_{Pt}} + \frac{w_C}{w_{Pt}\rho_C} + \frac{w_N}{(1-w_N)w_{Pt}\rho_N} \right) \quad (9)$$

where m_{Pt} is the platinum loading in g cm^{-2} , L is the catalyst layer thickness in cm, ρ_C , ρ_{Pt} and ρ_N are densities of carbon, platinum and Nafion taken as 2.0 g cm^{-3} , 21.5 g cm^{-3} and 1.8 g cm^{-3} , respectively. The composition of the heterogeneous mixture of platinum and carbon, i.e., platinum deposited on the carbon support, is described by the respective mass fractions w_{Pt} and w_C ($w_{Pt} + w_C = 1$), while the Nafion mass fraction w_N refers to the entire mass of CL. The mass fractions of the components were calculated from the composition of the ink: $w_{Pt} = 0.290$, $w_C = 0.710$ and $w_N = 0.298$. The results are collected in Table 3.

3.4. Microstructure of catalyst layers

To obtain more detailed information on the internal structure of the

Table 3

Platinum loading m_{Pt} , thickness L (determined using the Compact Layer Method) and total porosity ϵ_v calculated using Eq. (9) of catalyst layers on GDL.

Sample ID	$m_{Pt} / \text{mg cm}^{-2}$	$L / \mu\text{m}$	ϵ_v
USC 10L	0.047	4.41	0.78
USC 20L	0.074	5.72	0.73
USC 30L	0.115	7.71	0.69
USC 40L	0.146	9.22	0.67
IJP 6L	0.090	4.64	0.60
IJP 9L	0.141	6.34	0.54
IJP 12L	0.178	7.57	0.51
IJP 15L	0.238	9.56	0.48

catalyst layers and to verify the trends suggested by surface analysis and fuel cell performance, FIB-SEM tomography was used to reconstruct and examine their 3D microstructures. The 3D reconstruction of the CLs microstructure allows a direct visual and mathematical assessment of porosity, phase connectivity, and isotropy. Two thinnest CLs labelled IJP 6L and USC 10L were selected for this study. Thin layers are less prone to a structure collapse during the FIB milling than the thicker layers. Additionally, thin layers with low Pt loading are more interesting from the application point of view. Resulting primary volume images were processed by combining the 3D anisotropic diffusion filter and segmentation based on the watershed algorithm [29,30]. As a result, the visualisation of the reconstructed void and solid phases distribution was obtained (see Fig. 5). The segmented data was stored as an indicator function uniquely assigning each point in the 3D discrete space to either a void phase (pore) or a solid phase. Before any use, the indicator functions were checked for the presence of isolated (discontinuous) clusters of solid phases in the inner regions. Because their existence is non-physical, all solid phase clusters were identified using the 6-neighbour connectivity rule. Those clusters not connected to the rest of the solid phase in the inner regions were excluded from further considerations [43]. This operation slightly increased the void phase fraction, say by about 2×10^{-4} . There is no physical reason for a similar operation with the void phase because isolated pores may exist. However, to keep the original porosity, all isolated pore clusters consisting of less than a specified number of voxels were replaced with solid-phase voxels. We note that the clustering of the void phase was governed by the 26-neighbour connectivity rule. The indicator functions serve then as key

Fig. 4. Dependence of catalyst layer thickness on Pt loading.

Fig. 5. 3D replicas of catalyst layers from FIB-SEM tomography supplemented with pore space skeletons: A) IJP 6L and B) USC 10L. Dimensions of the insets: IJP CL 2945 nm \times 1855 nm \times 1405 nm, IJP MPL 3415 nm \times 1955 nm \times 1405 nm, USC CL 4090 nm \times 3050 nm \times 3690 nm, USC MPL 4185 nm \times 2050 nm \times 3690 nm.

inputs for all subsequent calculations, including statistical measures, random-walk simulations and permeability calculations. Note that the term replica is used in this study for the indicator function. Basic microstructural characteristics of the reconstructed samples of IJP 6L and USC 10L are collected in Table 4.

The void fractions ϕ_v in Table 4 represent the values averaged over the entire 3D regions, the sizes of which are given there. Since the volume fractions of both replicas differ little, their microstructure can be tentatively characterized as similar. The isolated porosity, which is negligible in both cases, can also be seen as a reconstruction artefact. Fluctuations of $S_1^{(v)}$ around ϕ_v are shown in the top row of Fig. 6.

Table 4

Basic characteristics of FIB-SEM replicas: size in voxels, total porosity ϕ_v , isolated porosity ϕ_{vi} , specific surface s (interface area per unit sample volume) and interface area per unit pore volume s/ϕ_v . The voxel size is 5 nm in both cases.

Replica	Size, voxel	ϕ_v	ϕ_{vi}	$s / \mu\text{m}^{-1}$	$s \phi_v^{-1} / \mu\text{m}^{-1}$
R-IJP 6L	1685 \times 451 \times 282	0.4004	0.0009	14.8	36.9
R-USC 10L	2079 \times 817 \times 739	0.3826	0.0007	12.3	32.1

Although these fluctuations are quite large for both replicas, there are no significant differences between the courses measured in the principal directions. In addition, most of the region V shows a local volume fraction in the interval from 0.3 to 0.5. Therefore, the microstructures of R-IJP 6L and R-USC 10L (excluding cracks) appear to be statistically homogeneous. Thus, the replicas can be considered as representative elementary volumes of both CLs. However, it must be kept in mind that the replicas are small, which limits the significance of the conclusions.

The sizes of the spherical regions that fit into the void or solid phase are shown in the middle row of Fig. 6. The density probability functions $P^{(v)}$ and $P^{(s)}$ decrease very rapidly near the origin, indicating the presence of a large number of small spherical regions at the edges of other, more compact regions of both phases. The solid phase of both replicas forms spherical regions with radii between 10 nm and 40 nm, which are approximately equally represented, see the flat regions of the blue curves. The functions $P^{(v)}$ do not show a similar behaviour for either replica, i.e., they do not involve flat regions. Considering that $\phi_v = 0.4004$ for R-IJP 6L, it is interesting that the largest spherical regions in the void phase are even larger than the largest spherical regions in the solid phase, see the blue line crossing the red one in Fig. 6. In contrast,

Fig. 6. (Top row) The one-point probability functions for samples IJP 6L (A) and USC 10L (B) shown in the three principal directions. Horizontal spans of the curves in the individual directions are related to the replica sizes given in Table 4. (Middle row) The “pore-size” functions for the void (v) and solid (s) phases. R-IJP 6L: $\langle \delta_v \rangle = 27.0$ nm, $\langle \delta_s \rangle = 32.4$ nm, R-USC 10L: $\langle \delta_v \rangle = 31.3$ nm, $\langle \delta_s \rangle = 40.6$ nm. (Bottom row) The two-point cluster function for the void phase versus the length u of line segment: R-IJP 6L (E); R-USC 10L (F). The functional values $C_2^{(v)}$ for long distances ($u > 1.1$ μm), not shown in the charts, stay above positive values around 0.15 and 0.14, respectively.

for R-USC 10L, the spherical regions in the solid phase are larger than their counterparts in the void phase over the entire range of radii. From the courses of $F^{(v)}$ and $F^{(s)}$ and the mean radii in the caption of Fig. 6D), it is also seen that the spherical regions in R-USC 10L are larger than those in R-IJP 6L. From the analysis of the microstructure of both phases so far, it can be concluded that the IJP 6L replica is made up of smaller particles than the USC 10L replica, which is accompanied by the existence of

smaller pores in the IJP 6L replica compared to the USC 10L replica.

In addition to the size of the spherical regions, the connectivity of both phases is also important for the transport properties. As mentioned earlier, the solid phase must form a single cluster to be physically feasible. This means that the solid phase must form a single cluster connected in all three principal directions. The final reconstruction phase ensured this. The void phase was also found to form a single

dominant cluster connected in all three principal directions in both replicas. Since the closed porosity represents a marginal fraction of the total porosity, its influence on the transport properties can be expected to be negligible. Good connectivity of the void phase along all three principal directions is also demonstrated in the bottom row of Fig. 6 where the two-point cluster function $C_2^{(v)}$ maintains a positive value even for sampling line segments with a length comparable to the replica size. In addition, connectivity of the void phase along the third principal direction is better than connectivity in the first two principal directions when the sampling line segment is shorter than $0.5 \mu\text{m}$ and $0.8 \mu\text{m}$ for R-IJP 6L and R-USC 10L, respectively.

When comparing the void fraction obtained from FIB-SEM tomography with the porosity values calculated from composition and profilometry-based thickness (Table 3), the FIB-SEM values are consistently lower. This discrepancy is consistent with previous reports in the literature [38] and can be attributed to several factors. First, both the carbon support and the catalyst layer contain pores smaller than the resolution limit of FIB-SEM, which leads to an underestimation of total porosity in the reconstructed volume. Second, the FIB-SEM analysis was performed on a relatively homogeneous region deeper within the CL, whereas significant surface roughness especially near cracks and agglomerates is not captured in the imaged volume. Third, this surface roughness introduces uncertainty in thickness measurements obtained by profilometry (see Fig. S9). This uncertainty propagates into the porosity values derived from bulk composition and layer thickness. The effect is more pronounced for the USC layers exhibiting higher surface roughness, more important crack fraction, and more frequent surface agglomerates. These features likely contribute to the larger observed discrepancy between FIB-SEM and bulk-derived porosity in USC samples compared to IJP.

The data in Table 4 was also verified by determining the total specific

surface area of the USC catalyst layer by the BET method. The obtained value of $34.9 \text{ m}^2 \text{ g}^{-1}$ was recalculated using the apparent density 0.524 g cm^{-3} determined from the formulas and data in Section 3.3. The transformed value is found to be $18.3 \mu\text{m}^{-1}$, which corresponds well with the value of $12.3 \mu\text{m}^{-1}$ in Table 4. Unlike the total porosity, the specific surface area measured using the BET method is little affected by cracks, surface roughness and large pores, since the main fraction of the surface area is found in narrow pores, if these are sufficiently numerous.

3.5. Pore size distribution estimated using mercury porosimetry

As a technique complementary to BET, mercury porosimetry was used to study a wider pore size distribution beyond the resolution of FIB-SEM. We note that a direct comparison of the observed porosity and pore size distribution is not possible for at least three reasons. First, the sample sizes for mercury porosimetry and FIB-SEM reconstruction are incommensurable. Therefore, wide pores cannot be registered in the small samples prepared for FIB-SEM. Second, narrow pores (with diameters smaller than 25 nm) are not visible in the FIB-SEM replicas. Third, the pore sizes estimated from the mercury capillary pressure curve are biased toward smaller values compared to reality, since the penetration of mercury into the pores is controlled by the narrowest cross-sections in the pore space, see [44]. For these reasons, we present only the capillary pressure curve of mercury for the USC catalyst layer in Fig. 7.

The curve can be divided into three parts, starting at the bottom right, which corresponds to the beginning of mercury intrusion. The first part of the curve between $3 \mu\text{m}$ and $70 \mu\text{m}$ indicates the presence of spaces between pieces of CL and large pores or rather cracks. These objects are not registered by FIB-SEM reconstruction, since the reconstructed regions are smaller. The next part of the curve is flat, which means the absence of pores with a radius from 60 nm to $3 \mu\text{m}$. The last

Fig. 7. Capillary pressure curve of mercury for USC. The external pressure of mercury p_{Hg} , MPa, was converted to the pore radius r_p , μm , using the Washburn equation (an advancing contact angle of 130° and a surface tension of mercury of 485 mN m^{-1} , i.e. $r_p = 0.6235/p_{\text{Hg}}$).

part of the curve captures the dependence of the volume of real CL pores on their radius. Approximately half of the volume of these pores is concentrated in pores with a radius of less than 10 nm, which will be important in interpreting the FIB-SEM reconstruction.

3.6. Transport properties of catalyst layers

With the microstructural framework established, the permeability and diffusivity of the CLs were quantified. These transport parameters are essential for efficient fuel cell operation and were interpreted in the context of observed microstructure. The transport parameters of the catalyst layer carrier, i.e., the GDL, were determined in the first step. A set of experimental data acquired in the range of absolute pressures from 2.5 kPa to 55 kPa ensured minimization of the objective function. The optimal values of κ and β were reached in five to seven iterations independently of their initial estimates. Specifically, the following values were found: $\kappa = 2.24 \times 10^{-7} \pm 9.9 \times 10^{-9}$ m and $\beta = 1.40 \times 10^{-13} \pm 4.0 \times 10^{-15}$ m². These facts indicated good reliability of the GDL transport parameters. Since the CL had narrower pores than the GDL, the mean Knudsen number in the catalyst pore space is expected to increase at a given absolute pressure. This corresponds to a shift in the transport mechanism in favour of Knudsen flow. In order to preserve a balanced representation of Knudsen and viscous flow, experiments performed at absolute pressures elevated up to 85 kPa were included. The optimum values of κ and β together with the corresponding confidence intervals for the catalyst layer are summarized in Table 5. The confidence interval values represent approximately 10 % of the parameters mean value.

Note that the confidence limits in Table 5 do not account for the non-uniform thickness of circular samples of layered porous bodies (catalyst layers + GDL) with a diameter of 6.2 mm. To assess the effect of modifying the catalyst layer thickness on the transport parameters, their calculation was repeated with the catalyst layer thickness changed by ± 10 % and ± 20 %. It was found that the values of κ and β correspondingly varied within ± 10 % and ± 20 %, respectively. Thus, the mean value of catalyst layer thickness and the values of κ and β were directly proportional. At the same time, it is clear that the uncertainty in the mean thickness value used did not cause significant changes in the values of κ and β . Comparing the permeability data in Table 5, we observe that both the IJP and USC methods result in catalyst layers with comparable gas transport properties. This similarity arises despite the notable differences between the two deposition techniques.

The experimental values of κ and β were further compared with their theoretical counterparts obtained by simulating the random walk in the Knudsen regime and solving the Stokes equation for a Newtonian incompressible fluid, respectively [29,30]. Results in the form of the main components of tensors related to Knudsen flow, i.e., κ_{11} , κ_{22} , κ_{33} , and viscous flow, i.e., β_{11} , β_{22} , β_{33} , are collected for the reconstructed microstructures of IJP 6L and USC-10L in Table 6, which allows comparing the differences between the effective transport properties along the principal directions. Significant differences between the third component and the first two components of the tensors suggest that both

Table 5

Experimentally determined transport parameters κ and β of the catalyst layers and the corresponding joint confidence limits σ_κ and σ_β calculated using the linearized model of the permeation cell at the 95 % probability level.

Sample	$h / \mu\text{m}$	κ / m	σ_κ / m	β / m^2	$\sigma_\beta / \text{m}^2$
USC 10L	3.6	5.85×10^{-9}	5.9×10^{-10}	9.46×10^{-16}	1.2×10^{-16}
USC 20L	4.9	8.38×10^{-9}	1.0×10^{-9}	2.34×10^{-15}	2.5×10^{-16}
USC 30L	7.0	6.31×10^{-9}	5.9×10^{-10}	1.56×10^{-15}	1.3×10^{-16}
USC 40L	8.5	3.09×10^{-9}	2.7×10^{-10}	7.24×10^{-16}	6.6×10^{-17}
IJP 6L	4.0	4.46×10^{-9}	4.9×10^{-10}	1.33×10^{-15}	1.3×10^{-16}
IJP 9L	6.0	9.07×10^{-9}	9.2×10^{-10}	1.62×10^{-15}	1.7×10^{-16}
IJP 12L	8.0	7.15×10^{-9}	7.3×10^{-10}	1.81×10^{-15}	1.9×10^{-16}
IJP 15L	9.0	5.32×10^{-9}	4.3×10^{-10}	8.27×10^{-16}	8.7×10^{-17}

microstructures are statistically anisotropic, cf. the courses of $C_2^{(v)}$ in Fig. 6. Note that the second principal direction associated with the second main component (κ_{22} or β_{22}) is perpendicular to the plane of the catalyst layer disc, which is also the direction in which the experimental values of the transport parameters in Table 5 were determined. In agreement with the experimental values, the calculated values of κ_{ii} and β_{ii} do not show a significant dependence on the CL type, which is also in agreement with the microstructural characterization in Fig. 6.

Of note is the unexpectedly good agreement between κ_{22} and experimental values of κ . In contrast, the calculated values of β_{22} are approximately more than one order of magnitude smaller than the experimental values of β in Table 5. This discrepancy can be explained by the presence of cracks discussed in the previous chapters. The greater sensitivity of creeping gas flow to cracks much wider than a typical pore in the CL follows from the differential form of the Darcy equation modified for gas (Eq. (10)).

$$N = \left(\kappa \sqrt{\frac{8R_g T}{\pi M}} + \frac{\beta R_g T c}{\mu} \right) \frac{dc}{d\xi} \quad (10)$$

where N is the molar flux, ξ is the spatial coordinate parallel to the direction of macroscopic flow, c is the molar concentration of gas, T is the absolute temperature, M is the molar mass of gas, μ is the viscosity and R_g is the gas constant. The second term in parentheses dominates the first term in wide pores, as β increases with the square of the characteristic pore size, compared to κ , which increases only linearly with pore size. Therefore, the experimental values of β in Table 5, which include the contribution of cracks, must be higher than those values shown in Table 6, which are associated with homogeneous microstructures of FIB-SEM replicas.

The final structural-function parameter of the CL investigated was the in-plane electrical conductivity. Differences in conductivity were correlated with microstructural factors, thus validating the results derived in the previous chapter. When connected with the deposition method, they further helped in clarifying its performance implications for fuel cell operation. The corresponding electrical conductivity values obtained utilizing the Compact Layer method thickness are presented in Fig. 8 (the catalyst layer conductivities obtained using all the thickness determination methods can be found in Fig. S10 in Supplementary information). On average, IJP layers exhibit higher conductivity ($448 \pm 135 \text{ S m}^{-1}$) than those deposited by USC ($387 \pm 96 \text{ S m}^{-1}$). No clear trend between conductivity and layer thickness was observed for either technique. Instead, a large spread of values is apparent, suggesting the presence of local inhomogeneities. These deviations may stem from factors such as microstructural defects, variations in crack formation, or contact resistances between individual layers introduced during deposition. Nevertheless, the overall higher conductivity of IJP CLs reinforces their potential for efficient PEMFC operation.

The average bulk conductivity S_{bulk} of the fully compressed catalyst layers was determined to be $742 \pm 31 \text{ S m}^{-1}$ (average values of the intersections of the fitted lines with the ordinate are in Fig. S11 in Supplementary information). This value is higher than the values obtained by the evaluation of the catalyst layer conductivity on FTO, which is expected due to minimal porosity of compressed layer and improved contact between catalyst particles.

Random-walk simulations of ordinary diffusion in the void and solid phases of both replicas provided the estimates of effective diffusivities and effective electrical conductivities, which can be found in Table 7. To eliminate the effect of a chosen diffusion pair on effective binary diffusivities, the primary simulation results were transformed into the geometric factor tensor with the main components ψ_{11} , ψ_{22} and ψ_{33} [29,30]. Analogously, the electrical conductivity of porous catalyst layers was related to that of compact (non-porous) catalysts. The result was the main components of the relative electrical conductivity tensor, i. e., g_{11} , g_{22} and g_{33} . It should be noted that both transport parameters

Table 6Calculated transport parameters of two reconstructed samples expressed as the main components of tensors κ and β .

Replica	κ_{11} / m	κ_{22} / m	κ_{33} / m	β_{11} / m^2	β_{22} / m^2	β_{33} / m^2
R-IJP 6L	2.60×10^{-9}	2.05×10^{-9}	6.85×10^{-9}	4.37×10^{-17}	2.91×10^{-17}	8.37×10^{-17}
R-USC 10L	3.09×10^{-9}	3.18×10^{-9}	8.70×10^{-9}	5.51×10^{-17}	4.84×10^{-17}	1.37×10^{-16}

Fig. 8. Average electrical conductivity of the catalyst layers evaluated from the measurement of catalyst layers on FTO glass and thickness evaluated by Compact Layer method is given as $S_{\text{CL,FTO}}$. The average bulk conductivity of the fully compressed catalyst layers is given as S_{bulk} . The average electrical conductivity calculated using the relative electrical conductivity tensors from Table 7 is given by S_{CL} .**Table 7**Main components of the geometric factor tensor, ψ_{ii} , and relative electrical conductivity tensor, g_{ii} . The average electrical conductivity is given by $S_{\text{CL}} = (g_{11} + g_{22} + g_{33}) S_{\text{BULK}} / 3$, where $S_{\text{BULK}} = 742 \text{ S m}^{-1}$. The electrical conductivity evaluated from the measurement of catalyst layers on FTO glass and thickness evaluated by Compact Layer method is given as $S_{\text{CL,FTO}}$.

Replica	Void phase			Solid phase			$S_{\text{CL}} / \text{S m}^{-1}$	$S_{\text{CL,FTO}} / \text{S m}^{-1}$
	ψ_{11}	ψ_{22}	ψ_{33}	g_{11}	g_{22}	g_{33}		
R-IJP 6L	0.108	0.103	0.209	0.337	0.359	0.438	281	448 ± 135
R-USC 10L	0.111	0.120	0.220	0.336	0.361	0.456	285	387 ± 96

could be directly compared with their experimental counterparts as they apply to the entire sample cross section. In agreement with previous findings, the effective properties associated with ordinary diffusion in the pores and the electrical conductivity of the solid phase are independent of the method of CL preparation. Also, the increased transport capability along the third principal direction agrees with previous calculations and indicates anisotropic properties of both catalyst layers.

The calculated values in Tables 6 and 7 associated with transport in pores can be examined using cross-property relations, such as the Kozeny–Carman formula $\beta = \frac{1}{2} \psi \phi_c^2 s^{-2}$ [45]. Substituting the ψ_{ii} values from Table 7 into this formula gives the values of β_{ii} in the intervals $[3.8 \times 10^{-17}, 7.7 \times 10^{-17}] \text{ m}^2$ and $[5.4 \times 10^{-17}, 1.1 \times 10^{-16}] \text{ m}^2$ for R-IJP 6L and R-USC 10L, respectively. The good agreement with the data in Table 6 is evident.

It is worth noting that the experimental value of S_{bulk} is in good agreement with the estimate calculated using the differential effective medium approximation introduced by Bruggeman [40]. Using this approximation scheme, the tiny platinum particles are assumed to be dispersed in a continuous matrix of carbon particles. Since platinum is

superconductive relative to amorphous carbon ($S_{\text{Pt}} / S_{\text{C}} \rightarrow \infty$), the effective conductivity $S_{\text{Pt/C}}$ is simply estimated as Eq. (11).

$$S_{\text{Pt/C}} = S_{\text{C}} \phi_{\text{C}}^{-3} \quad (11)$$

where ϕ_{C} is the volume fraction of carbon in Pt/C particles and S_{C} is the electrical conductivity of amorphous carbon particles (here $S_{\text{Pt}} = 9.43 \times 10^6 \text{ S m}^{-1}$ and $S_{\text{C}} \in [1250, 2000] \text{ S m}^{-1}$). After calculating the effective conductivity of the Pt/C composite, two options can be assumed. The Pt/C particles are either dispersed in the ionomer forming another continuous non-porous matrix, or the Pt/C particles are in contact with each other and the ionomer only partially envelops them, i.e., the Pt/C particles form the continuous phase. After choosing the role of the phases, the effective conductivity of the Pt/C/ionomer composite S_{ef} is evaluated using the full form of the Bruggeman model (Eq. (12)).

$$\left(\frac{S_{\text{dis}} - S_{\text{ef}}}{S_{\text{dis}} - S_{\text{con}}} \right) \left(\frac{S_{\text{con}}}{S_{\text{ef}}} \right)^{1/3} = \phi_{\text{con}} \quad (12)$$

where ϕ_{con} is the volume fraction of the continuous phase, S_{con} and S_{dis}

are the electrical conductivities of the continuous and dispersed phases, respectively. The volume fractions ϕ_C , ϕ_{Pt} and $\phi_{Pt/C}$ are calculated using the data on the mass composition and densities of the components in Section 3.3, specifically Eqs. (12)–(16),

$$\rho_{Pt/C} = \left(\frac{w_{Pt}}{\rho_{Pt}} + \frac{w_C}{\rho_C} \right)^{-1} \quad (13)$$

$$\phi_{Pt} = w_{Pt} \frac{\rho_{Pt/C}}{\rho_{Pt}} \quad (14)$$

$$\phi_C = 1 - \phi_{Pt} \quad (15)$$

$$\phi_N = \frac{w_N}{\rho_N} \left(\frac{w_N}{\rho_N} + \frac{1 - w_N}{\rho_{Pt/C}} \right)^{-1} \quad (16)$$

$$\phi_{Pt/C} = 1 - \phi_N \quad (17)$$

Because the electrical conductivity of the dry ionomer is negligible compared to the other components, i.e., $S_N/S_{Pt/C} \rightarrow 0$, the effective conductivity of the compressed CL with the ionomer as the continuous phase ($S_{con} = S_N$ and $S_{dis} = S_{Pt/C}$) is also negligible ($S_{ef} \rightarrow 0$). This is clearly unrealistic, since experimentally it is found $S_{bulk} = 742 \text{ S m}^{-1}$. After formally swapping the roles of the Pt/C and ionomer phases ($S_{con} = S_{Pt/C}$ and $S_{dis} = S_N$), the value of S_{ef} , according to the adopted conductivity of amorphous carbon, is in the range from 666 to 1065 S m^{-1} , which is in excellent agreement with the experimental observation. It can, therefore, be assumed that in the compressed catalyst layer the Pt/C particles form a continuous phase that is partially enveloped by the ionomer.

As a final note on the anisotropic structure, the properties along the third principal direction are found to differ from the first two directions. The third principal direction, however, is identical to the milling direction of the CL. Since the used FIB-SEM instrument operates at the limit of its capabilities with a voxel size of 5 nm, it is possible that the observed difference in the third principal direction is of an artefact nature. However, this is not a fundamental problem that invalidates the entire reconstruction, and the results based on it. What is important is that the first two principal directions correspond to the tangential and normal directions in the CLs and the microstructures and related properties in these two directions are isotropic. Therefore, both layers can be described here as statistically homogeneous and isotropic on the scale of the FIB-SEM reconstruction performed.

4. Conclusion

This study provides a comprehensive structure–property analysis of CLs fabricated by IJP and USC, building on the performance differences observed in operating PEMFCs based on the catalyst layers produced by these two methods. Despite both layers show relatively similar microscale porosity, IJP layer is made up of smaller particles than the USC layers, which is accompanied by the existence of smaller pores in the IJP layer compared to the USC layer. This results in differences in layers conductivity and transport properties, where IJP layers show approximately 15 % higher electrical conductivity, while USC layers have slightly higher permeability. Another aspect represents macroscale features, like crack formation, where cracks coverage on IJP layers' surface is in average 0.41 %, while 3.01 % of USC surface is covered. Furthermore, Pt distribution inhomogeneity is observed in the case of USC layers. The macroscale effects are particularly pronounced at low Pt loadings (below 0.2 mg cm^{-2}). These aspects explain superior performance of the MEAs based on catalyst layers produced by IJP observed experimentally. Due to this fact and considering its scalability, preciseness, and low waste, inkjet printing represents a highly promising approach for producing MEAs not only for PEMFCs, but also for other electrochemical devices requiring controlled thin-film architecture.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

M. Hala: Writing – original draft, Investigation, Data curation. **M. Prokop:** Writing – original draft, Methodology, Investigation, Data curation. **P. Capek:** Writing – original draft, Visualization, Software, Methodology, Investigation, Data curation. **M. Vesely:** Writing – original draft, Visualization, Investigation, Data curation. **T. Jedlicka:** Investigation. **T. Zubkova:** Writing – original draft, Investigation, Data curation. **K. Heinrich:** Investigation, Formal analysis. **A. Willert:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Project administration, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization. **R. Zichner:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Methodology, Conceptualization. **K. Bouzek:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Project administration, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization.

Declaration of Generative AI and AI-assisted technologies in the writing process

During the preparation of this work the authors used ChatGPT in order to improve the readability of the article. After using this tool/service, the authors reviewed and edited the content as needed and take full responsibility for the content of the published article.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Acknowledgement

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 958174.

This study is also based upon work supported by the NSF-GACR collaborative grant “NSF-GACR: Engineering nanostructured electrodes for the selective recovery of homogeneous catalysts” under Czech Science Foundation Grant number 24-10402L.

This work was supported by the project “The Energy Conversion and Storage”, funded as project No. CZ.02.01.01/00/22_008/0004617 by Programme Johannes Amos Comenius, call Excellent Research.

This research was funded by the Sächsische Aufbaubank (SAB) [No. 100634164], Germany. This project was co-financed with tax funds on the basis of the budget passed by the Saxon state parliament, Germany.

Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cej.2025.171283>.

Data availability

Data can be found at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15781389>

References

- [1] D.A. Cullen, K.C. Neyerlin, R.K. Ahluwalia, R. Mukundan, K.L. More, R.L. Borup, A. Z. Weber, D.J. Myers, A. Kusoglu, New roads and challenges for fuel cells in heavy-duty transportation, *Nat. Energy* 6 (5) (2021) 462–474, <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41560-021-00775-z>.
- [2] H. Nazir, N. Muthuswamy, C. Louis, S. Jose, J. Prakash, M.E.M. Buan, C. Flox, S. Chavan, X. Shi, P. Kauranen, T. Kallio, G. Maia, K. Tammeveski, N. Lympemperopoulos, E. Carcadea, E. Veziroglu, A. Iranzo, M.K. A. Is the H2 economy realizable in the foreseeable future? Part III: H2 usage technologies, applications, and challenges and opportunities, *Int. J. Hydrog. Energy* 45 (53) (2020) 28217–28239, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijhydene.2020.07.256>.
- [3] M. van der Spek, C. Banet, C. Bauer, P. Gabrielli, W. Goldthorpe, M. Mazzotti, S. T. Munkejord, N.A. Røkke, N. Shah, N. Sunny, D. Sutter, J.M. Trusler, M. Gazzani, Perspective on the hydrogen economy as a pathway to reach net-zero

- CO₂ emissions in Europe, *Energy Environ. Sci.* 15 (3) (2022) 1034–1077, <https://doi.org/10.1039/d1ee02118d>.
- [4] A.I. Atteya, D. Ali, M. Hossain, N. Sellami, A comprehensive review on the potential of green hydrogen in empowering the low-carbon economy: development status, ongoing trends and key challenges, *Green Energy Environ. Technol.* 2 (2023), <https://doi.org/10.5772/geet.23>.
- [5] X.-Z. Yuan, C. Nayoze-Coyne, N. Shaigan, D. Fisher, N. Zhao, N. Zamel, P. Gazdzicki, M. Ulsh, K.A. Friedrich, F. Girard, U. Groos, A review of functions, attributes, properties and measurements for the quality control of proton exchange membrane fuel cell components, *J. Power Sources* 491 (2021), <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jpowsour.2021.229540>.
- [6] T.A.M. Suter, K. Smith, J. Hack, L. Rasha, Z. Rana, G.M.A. Angel, P.R. Shearing, T. S. Miller, D.J.L. Brett, Engineering catalyst layers for next-generation polymer electrolyte fuel cells: a review of design, materials, and methods, *Adv. Energy Mater.* 11 (37) (2021), <https://doi.org/10.1002/aenm.202101025>.
- [7] Y. Sun, S. Polani, F. Luo, S. Ott, P. Strasser, F. Dionigi, Advancements in cathode catalyst and cathode layer design for proton exchange membrane fuel cells, *Nat. Commun.* 12 (1) (2021) 5984, <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-021-25911-x>.
- [8] J. Zhao, H. Liu, X. Li, Structure, property, and performance of catalyst layers in proton exchange membrane fuel cells, *Electrochem. Energy Rev.* 6 (1) (2023) 13, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s41918-022-00175-1>.
- [9] B.H. Lim, E.H. Majlan, A. Tajuddin, T. Husaini, W.R. Wan Daud, N.A. Mohd Radzuan, M.A. Haque, Comparison of catalyst-coated membranes and catalyst-coated substrate for PEMFC membrane electrode assembly: a review, *Chin. J. Chem. Eng.* 33 (2021) 1–16, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cjche.2020.07.044>.
- [10] P. Liu, D. Yang, B. Li, C. Zhang, P. Ming, Recent progress of catalyst ink for roll-to-roll manufacturing paired with slot die coating for proton exchange membrane fuel cells, *Int. J. Hydrog. Energy* 48 (51) (2023) 19666–19685, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijhydene.2023.02.022>.
- [11] C. Daniel, D. Wood III, G. Krumdick, M. Ulsh, V. Battaglia, P. Schunk, F. Crowson, Roll-to-Roll Advanced Materials Manufacturing DoE Laboratory Collaboration - Early Stage R&D - FY 2020 Final Report, 2021, <https://doi.org/10.2172/1814323>.
- [12] S. Towne, V. Viswanathan, J. Holbery, P. Rieke, Fabrication of polymer electrolyte membrane fuel cell MEAs utilizing inkjet print technology, *J. Power Sources* 171 (2) (2007) 575–584, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jpowsour.2007.07.017>.
- [13] A.D. Taylor, E.Y. Kim, V.P. Humes, J. Kizuka, L.T. Thompson, Inkjet printing of carbon supported platinum 3-D catalyst layers for use in fuel cells, *J. Power Sources* 171 (1) (2007) 101–106, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jpowsour.2007.01.024>.
- [14] M.S. Saha, M. Tam, V. Berejnov, D. Susac, S. McDermaid, A.P. Hitchcock, J. Stumper, Characterization and performance of catalyst layers prepared by inkjet printing technology, *ECS Trans.* 58 (1) (2013) 797–806, <https://doi.org/10.1149/05801.0797ecst>.
- [15] S. Shukla, K. Domican, K. Karan, S. Bhattacharjee, M. Secanell, Analysis of low platinum loading thin polymer electrolyte fuel cell electrodes prepared by inkjet printing, *Electrochim. Acta* 156 (2015) 289–300, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.electacta.2015.01.028>.
- [16] A. Lesch, F. Cortes-Salazar, V.C. Bassetto, V. Amstutz, H.H. Girault, Inkjet printing meets electrochemical energy conversion, *Chimia (Aarau)* 69 (5) (2015) 284–289, <https://doi.org/10.2533/chimia.2015.284>.
- [17] L.J. Deiner, T.L. Reitz, Inkjet and aerosol jet printing of electrochemical devices for energy conversion and storage, *Adv. Eng. Mater.* 19 (7) (2017) 1600878, <https://doi.org/10.1002/adem.201600878>.
- [18] M. Mandal, A. Valls, N. Gangnus, M. Secanell, Analysis of inkjet printed catalyst coated membranes for polymer electrolyte electrolyzers, *J. Electrochem. Soc.* 165 (7) (2018) F543, <https://doi.org/10.1149/2.1101807jes>.
- [19] C.A. Gomes Bezerra, L.J. Deiner, G. Tremilosti-Filho, Unexpected performance of inkjet-printed membrane electrode assemblies for proton exchange membrane fuel cells, *Adv. Eng. Mater.* 21 (11) (2019) 1900703, <https://doi.org/10.1002/adem.201900703>.
- [20] Y. Tamaki, K. Sugiura, Influence of the catalyst layer structure formed by inkjet coating printer on pefc performance, *Polymers* (2021), <https://doi.org/10.3390/polym13060899>.
- [21] A. Willert, F.Z. Tabary, T. Zubkova, P.E. Santangelo, M. Romagnoli, R.R. Baumann, Multilayer additive manufacturing of catalyst-coated membranes for polymer electrolyte membrane fuel cells by inkjet printing, *Int. J. Hydrog. Energy* 47 (48) (2022) 20973–20986, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijhydene.2022.04.197>.
- [22] S. Shukla, D. Stanier, M.S. Saha, J. Stumper, M. Secanell, Analysis of inkjet printed PEFC electrodes with varying platinum loading, *J. Electrochem. Soc.* 163 (7) (2016) F677, <https://doi.org/10.1149/2.1111607jes>.
- [23] A. Strong, C. Thornberry, S. Beattie, R. Chen, S.R. Coles, Depositing catalyst layers in polymer electrolyte membrane fuel cells: a review, *J. Fuel Cell Sci. Technol.* 12 (6) (2015), <https://doi.org/10.1115/1.4031961>.
- [24] S. Shukla, K. Domican, M. Secanell, Effect of electrode patterning on PEM fuel cell performance using ink-jet printing method, *ECS Trans.* 64 (3) (2014) 341–352, <https://doi.org/10.1149/06403.0341ecst>.
- [25] Q. Shen, S. Dong, S. Li, G. Yang, Numerical study on performance of HT-PEMFC with gradient design of Pt loading, *Electrochim. Acta* (2023) 142326, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.electacta.2023.142326>.
- [26] E. Dong, H. Zhao, R. Zhang, L. Chen, W.-Q. Tao, Effects of gradient structures of cathode catalyst layers on performance and durability of proton exchange membrane fuel cells, *Electrochim. Acta* 477 (2024), <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.electacta.2024.143772>.
- [27] T. Zubkova, K. Heinrich, M. Hala, M. Prokop, T. Jedlicka, K. Bouzek, A. Willert, R. Zichner, Advanced catalyst layers for PEM fuel cell produced by inkjet printing: catalyst layer optimisation and comparison with ultrasonic-spray-coated one, *Fuel* 407 (2026) 137376, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fuel.2025.137376>.
- [28] M.A. Sadeghi, Z.A. Khan, M. Agnaou, L. Hu, S. Litster, A. Kongkanand, E. Padgett, D.A. Muller, T. Friscic, J. Gostick, Predicting PEMFC performance from a volumetric image of catalyst layer structure using pore network modeling, *Appl. Energy* 353 (2024) 122004, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apenergy.2023.122004>.
- [29] M. Prokop, M. Vesely, P. Capek, M. Páidar, K. Bouzek, High-temperature PEM fuel cell electrode catalyst layers part I: microstructure reconstructed using FIB-SEM tomography and its calculated effective transport properties, *Electrochim. Acta* 413 (2022) 140133, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.electacta.2022.140133>.
- [30] M. Prokop, P. Capek, M. Vesely, M. Páidar, K. Bouzek, High-temperature PEM fuel cell electrode catalyst layers Part 2: experimental validation of its effective transport properties, *Electrochim. Acta* 413 (2022), <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.electacta.2022.140121>.
- [31] C. Zhao, S. Yuan, X. Cheng, Z. Zheng, J. Liu, J. Yin, S. Shen, X. Yan, J. Zhang, The effect of catalyst layer design on catalyst utilization in PEMFC studied via stochastic reconstruction method, *Energy AI* 13 (2023), <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.egyai.2023.100245>.
- [32] W.K. Epting, J. Gelb, S. Litster, Resolving the three-dimensional microstructure of polymer electrolyte fuel cell electrodes using nanometer-scale X-ray computed tomography, *Adv. Funct. Mater.* 22 (3) (2012) 555–560, <https://doi.org/10.1002/adfm.201101525>.
- [33] H.-R.M. Jong, F.R. Brushett, P.J.A. Kenis, The effects of catalyst layer deposition methodology on electrode performance, *Adv. Energy Mater.* 3 (5) (2013) 589–599, <https://doi.org/10.1002/aenm.201200759>.
- [34] J. Hack, T.M.M. Heenan, F. Iacoviello, N. Mansor, Q. Meyer, P. Shearing, N. Brandon, D.J.L. Brett, A structure and durability comparison of membrane electrode assembly fabrication methods: self-assembled versus hot-pressed, *J. Electrochem. Soc.* 165 (6) (2018) F3045, <https://doi.org/10.1149/2.0051806jes>.
- [35] G. Inoue, K. Yokoyama, J. Ooyama, T. Terao, T. Tokunaga, N. Kubo, M. Kawase, Theoretical examination of effective oxygen diffusion coefficient and electrical conductivity of polymer electrolyte fuel cell porous components, *J. Power Sources* 327 (2016) 610–621, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jpowsour.2016.07.107>.
- [36] Y. Gao, Using MRT lattice Boltzmann method to simulate gas flow in simplified catalyst layer for different inlet–outlet pressure ratio, *Int. J. Heat Mass Transf.* 88 (2015) 122–132, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijheatmasstransfer.2015.04.031>.
- [37] S. Shukla, F. Wei, M. Mandal, J. Zhou, M.S. Saha, J. Stumper, M. Secanell, Determination of PEFC gas diffusion layer and catalyst layer porosity utilizing Archimedes principle, *J. Electrochem. Soc.* 166 (15) (2019) F1142, <https://doi.org/10.1149/2.0251915jes>.
- [38] M. Sabharwal, L.M. Pant, A. Putz, D. Susac, J. Jankovic, M. Secanell, Analysis of catalyst layer microstructures: from imaging to performance, *Fuel Cells* 16 (6) (2016) 734–753, <https://doi.org/10.1002/fuce.201600008>.
- [39] K. Singh, N. Paliwal, K. Kasamias, Surface roughness characterization using representative elementary area (REA) analysis, *Sci. Rep.* 14 (1) (2024) 1785, <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-024-52329-4>.
- [40] S. Torquato, *Random Heterogeneous Materials*, 2002, <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4757-6355-3>.
- [41] E. Sowade, J. Hammerschmidt, T. Blaudeck, R.R. Baumann, In-flight inkjet self-assembly of spherical nanoparticle aggregates, *Adv. Eng. Mater.* 14 (1–2) (2012) 98–100, <https://doi.org/10.1002/adem.201100245>.
- [42] Q. Wang, M. Eikerling, D. Song, Z. Liu, T. Navessin, Z. Xie, S. Holdcroft, Functionally graded cathode catalyst layers for polymer electrolyte fuel cells: I. Theoretical modeling, *J. Electrochem. Soc.* 151 (7) (2004) A950, <https://doi.org/10.1149/1.1753580>.
- [43] P. Diblíková, M. Veselý, P. Sysel, P. Čapek, Reconstructing the microstructure of polyimide-silicilate mixed-matrix membranes and their particle connectivity using FIB-SEM tomography, *J. Microsc.* 269 (3) (2018) 230–246, <https://doi.org/10.1111/jmi.12618>.
- [44] F.A.L. Dullien, I. - Pore structure, in: F.A.L. Dullien (Ed.), *Porous Media*, Second edition, Academic Press, San Diego, 1992, pp. 5–115, <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-12-223651-8.50007-9>.
- [45] L.M. Schwartz, N. Martys, D.P. Bentz, E.J. Garboczi, S. Torquato, Cross-property relations and permeability estimation in model porous media, *Phys. Rev. E* 48 (6) (1993) 4584–4591, <https://doi.org/10.1103/PhysRevE.48.4584>.
- [46] B.G. Pollet, A novel method for preparing PEMFC electrodes by the ultrasonic and sonoelectrochemical techniques, *Electrochem. Commun.* 11 (7) (2009) 1445–1448, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.elecom.2009.05.027>.
- [47] B. Millington, V. Whipple, B.G. Pollet, A novel method for preparing proton exchange membrane fuel cell electrodes by the ultrasonic-spray technique, *J. Power Sources* 196 (20) (2011) 8500–8508, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jpowsour.2011.06.024>.
- [48] Z. Turtayeva, F. Xu, J. Dillet, K. Mozet, R. Peignier, A. Celzard, G. Maranzana, Manufacturing catalyst-coated membranes by ultrasonic spray deposition for PEMFC: identification of key parameters and their impact on PEMFC performance, *Int. J. Hydrog. Energy* 47 (36) (2022) 16165–16178, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijhydene.2022.03.043>.